

Activated Carbon as an Adsorbent for Basic Yellow Dye. Part II—Surface Mass Transfer Processes

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A three step adsorption model has been proposed for the adsorption of Basic Yellow 2G dye on activated carbon. The surface mass transfer coefficients have been determined and correlated as the dimensionless mass transfer term $Sh/Sc^{0.33}$, as a function of agitation, initial dye concentration, carbon particle size, temperature and mass of carbon.

SLURRY reactors have features (isothermal operation, reaction at constant composition, simple construction, and stable characteristics) which may be advantageous in comparison with other types of reactors. However, retardation of the rate due to several mass transfer resistances can occur. In recent years information has been obtained on gas bubble to liquid mass transport^{1,2} and on bulk liquid to particle mass transport³⁻⁵.

The aim of this paper is to develop a model which would explain the removal of dye from effluent by adsorption onto the surface of activated carbon. Only surface mass transport will be considered and the transfer coefficients are correlated as a function of the dimensionless Sherwood number. All experimental details and results are presented in Part I of this paper⁶. Considerable attention was given to the design of the adsorber so that the power number is 9.5 for an agitation of 400 rpm.

Adsorption Isotherms: Adsorption isotherms were measured by introducing a known mass of carbon into 50 ml dye solutions of varying concentrations and agitating until equilibrium was achieved. The results are plotted according to the Langmuir equation in Fig. 1 and the numerical

Fig. 1. Langmuir analysis for the adsorption of Basic Yellow 2G on activated carbon.

expression for the isotherm is

$$n = \frac{4.0 \times 10^4 C}{1 + 2.4 \times 10^6 C} \quad \dots (1)$$

and the general Langmuir expression is given by equation (2).

$$n = \frac{KC}{1 + aC} \quad \dots (2)$$

Fig. 2 shows the dye uptake at equilibrium.

Fig. 2. Amount of Basic Yellow 2G dye, \bar{x}/M mg dye g^{-1} carbon, adsorbed onto activated carbon at equilibrium.

Theoretical analysis: Approximately 20 min after the start of each run, the rate of dye removal falls off to give a smooth curve. This part of the plot is due to intraparticle diffusion and shall be discussed in Part III⁷.

The initial portion of the plot can be interpreted by supposing a three-step model⁴ as follows: (1) mass transfer of dye from the bulk solution to the particle surface; (2) intraparticle diffusion and (3) adsorption at an interior site.

It is assumed that step 3 is rapid with respect to the first two steps. In a well-agitated slurry adsorber, mixing in the liquid phase is rapid. Hence the

concentration C_i^* of adsorbate and concentration m of carbon particles in the liquid are nearly uniform throughout the vessel. Then the change in C_i with respect to time is related to the fluid-particle mass transfer coefficient by the equations,

$$\frac{dC_i}{dt} = -k_s S_s (C_i - C_s) \quad \dots (3)$$

$$C_i = C_o (t=0) \quad \dots (4)$$

where C_s is the concentration in the liquid at outer surface particle.

The differential mass balance of dye within the particle is, assuming a constant total, effective intraparticle diffusivity, D_i

$$D_i \left(\frac{\partial^2 C_r}{\partial r^2} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{\partial C_r}{\partial r} \right) - \rho_p \frac{\partial n_r}{\partial t} = \epsilon_p \frac{\partial C_r}{\partial t} \quad \dots (5)$$

where C_r is concentration in liquid-filled pores at radius r , n_r is the concentration of adsorbed dye at radius r of the particle, ρ_p is the density of carbon particles and ϵ_p is the porosity of the carbon particles.

Boundary and initial conditions are,

$$D_i \left(\frac{\partial C_r}{\partial r} \right) = k_s (C_i - C_s) \quad \dots (6)$$

$$\frac{\partial C_r}{\partial r} = 0 (r=0) \quad \dots (7)$$

$$C_r = 0 (t=0) \quad \dots (8)$$

Since the equilibrium is assumed for Step 3, n_r and C_r are related by the isotherm, or

$$\frac{\partial n_r}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial C_r} \left(\frac{K C_r}{1 + a C_r} \right) \frac{\partial C_r}{\partial t} \quad \dots (9)$$

Equations 2-9 can be solved numerically to relate the observed C_i vs t curves to the rate coefficients, k_s and D_i .

A simpler procedure can be employed to obtain k_s . Since C_s approaches zero and C_i approaches C_o as t goes to zero, the equation 3 shows that,

$$d \left(\frac{C_i}{C_o} \right) = -k_s S_s \quad \dots (10)$$

Hence, the slope at $t=0$ of a plot of C_i/C_o vs t is equal to $-k_s S_s$. From such slopes k_s can be extracted.

When intraparticle diffusion is negligible and when the isotherm is linear, an analytical solution for C_i vs t is possible. Since $C_r = C_s$ and n_r is also uniform throughout the particle, equations 5 and 6 may be replaced by :

$$m \frac{dn}{dt} = k_s S_s (C_i - C_s) \quad \dots (11)$$

Also equation 9 becomes,

$$\frac{dn}{dt} = K \frac{dC_s}{dt} \quad \dots (12)$$

The value of S_s for a particle size range 500-710 microns is found to be 1.034 cm^{-1} where S_s is the

outer surface of carbon particles per unit volume of particle free slurry. The outer surface area of the particles was obtained from m by assuming spherical particles of diameter d_p that is

$$S_s = \frac{6m}{d_p \rho_t (1 - \epsilon_p)}$$

Equations 3, 11 and 12 with initial conditions (4) and $n=0$ at $t=0$ can be solved analytically to give

$$C_i/C_o = \frac{1}{1+mK} + \frac{mK}{1+mK} \exp - \frac{1+mK}{mK} k_s S_s t \quad \dots (13)$$

Equation (13) is not helpful for deciding if intraparticle diffusion affects the adsorption in our case, since the isotherm is not linear.

From the contact time results obtained, the mass transfer coefficient between bulk liquid and outer surface of particles, k_s can be obtained from the initial slope of the C_i/C_o vs t curve. However, the uncertainty in evaluating the slope of a curve at $t=0$ can be avoided by using equation (13). This expression shows that a plot of,

$$\ln \left[C_i/C_o - \frac{1}{1+mK} \right] \text{ vs } t$$

will give a straight line at $t=0$. Equation 13 is applicable at $t=0$ since the influence of intraparticle diffusion does not yet affect the results and since the isotherm becomes linear as time approaches zero.

From the initial values of $-\frac{1+mK}{mK} k_s S_s$ vs time,

k_s can be evaluated. By convention it is usual to report the k_s values obtained for the various runs in the form of a dimensionless correlation $Sh/(Sc)^{0.33}$. The molecular diffusivity of dye in water was obtained from the Wilke-Chang correlation and calculated to be $3.87 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}$ at 18°

The data relating to the properties of activated carbon are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PROPERTIES OF ACTIVATED CARBON

Solid phase density, kg m^{-3}	2040
Particle density, kg m^{-3}	960
Surface area, $\text{m}^2 \text{ kg}^{-1}$ (Nitrogen BET method)	500
Porosity, ϵ_p	0.53

Discussion

(i) *Effect of agitation* : The surface mass transfer coefficients, k_s , were determined for various degrees of agitation and the values are listed in Table 2. Fig. 3 shows a plot of $Sh/Sc^{0.33}$ against agitation (rpm) on logarithmic co-ordinates and the plot is linear. The results indicate that for Basic Yellow 2G dye, the rate of colour removal from the bulk solution by mass transport to the external surface sites of the activated carbon is controlled by the degree of agitation. Thus the effect of increasing the stirring rate is to decrease the film

* Explanations of symbols are given at the end.

Fig. 3. The adsorption of Basic Yellow 2G dye on activated carbon for various initial dye concentrations.

resistance to mass transfer surrounding the adsorbent particle.

TABLE 2—SURFACE MASS TRANSFER COEFFICIENTS FOR VARIOUS EXPERIMENTAL CONDITIONS

Agitation, rpm	150	200	400	500	600
k_s , $\text{cm s}^{-1} (\times 10^4)$	2.81	2.81	3.55	3.96	3.98
Dye Concentration, mg dm^{-3}	50	100	200	300	400
k_s , $\text{cm s}^{-1} (\times 10^4)$	25.2	25.2	6.90	2.62	1.62
Carbon Particle Size, microns	780	605	427	302	—
k_s , $\text{cm s}^{-1} (\times 10^4)$	3.33	3.30	3.52	3.77	—
Temperature $^{\circ}\text{C}$	20	40	60	80	—
k_s , $\text{cm s}^{-1} (\times 10^4)$	2.37	3.80	8.84	29.0	—
Carbon Mass, g	2.6	3.0	3.4	3.8	4.6
k_s , $\text{cm s}^{-1} (\times 10^4)$	2.80	3.60	4.17	6.18	6.34

(ii) *Effect of initial dye concentration*: Using the three-step adsorption model as in the previous section, the value of the surface mass transfer coefficient was obtained from the initial slope of the $\ln C_t/C_0 - \frac{1}{1+mk}$ against t plot. The k_s values at different initial dye concentrations are listed in Table 2 and it is observed that the transfer coefficients increase with decreasing dye concentrations. The reason for the decrease is the result of the boundary condition $C_t=C_0$ at $t=0$ and k_s is dependent on the concentration change relative to C_0 and not the absolute mass of dye adsorbed. At $t=0$, C_0 is different for each concentration run. Fig. 4 shows the plot of $\text{Sh}/\text{Sc}^{0.33}$ against C_0 using logarithmic co-ordinates and the plot is linear.

(iii) *Effect of particle size range*: The value of k_s is determined for each particle size range by the previous technique and the values obtained are given in Table 2. It is found that increasing the mean particle diameter results in an increase in k_s . This can be explained by the fact that for small particles a large surface area is presented to the dye molecules in the solution which results in a lower driving force and hence low values for k_s . The opposite effect occurs for large adsorbent particles.

The arithmetic mean particle diameter was used and the corresponding S_v values required in the

Fig. 4. The adsorption of Basic Yellow 2G dye on activated carbon for various initial dye concentrations.

determination of k_s are shown in Table 3. The mass transfer data are presented in the form of a log-log plot of $\text{Sh}/\text{Sc}^{0.33}$ and particle diameter and a linear graph is obtained (Fig. 5).

TABLE 3—CARBON PARTICLE SIZE RANGES AND SPECIFIC SURFACES

Particle size range (microns)	Mean diameter, d_p (cm)	Specific surface, S_v (cm^{-1})
250-355	302.5×10^{-4}	0.414
355-500	427.5×10^{-4}	0.298
500-710	605×10^{-4}	0.207
710-850	780×10^{-4}	0.161

Fig. 5. The adsorption of Basic Yellow 2G dye on activated carbon for various carbon particle size ranges.

(iv) *Effect of temperature*: The effect of temperature on the surface mass transfer coefficient was studied by performing experiments at 20, 40, 60 and 80° . The Sherwood and Schmidt numbers must be modified to incorporate the effect of temperature on the molecular diffusivity and

kinematic viscosity. The data are listed in Table 4. The k_s values show a significant increase as the temperature increases and are listed in Table 2. The plot of $Sh/Sc^{0.33}$ against $T^\circ K$ is linear using logarithmic co-ordinates (Fig. 6).

TABLE 4—MOLECULAR DIFFUSIVITIES, D ; KINEMATIC VISCOSITIES, ν ; AND DENSITIES, ρ AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temperature ($^\circ C$)	Kinematic viscosity ($cm^2 s^{-1}$)	Density ($kg m^{-3}$)	Molecular diffusivity ($cm^2 s^{-1}$)
20	1.007×10^{-3}	999.0	3.89×10^{-6}
40	0.661×10^{-3}	992.3	6.38×10^{-6}
60	0.477×10^{-3}	983.2	9.34×10^{-6}
80	0.367×10^{-3}	971.8	15.78×10^{-6}

Fig. 6. The adsorption of Basic Yellow 2G dye on activated carbon at various temperatures.

(v) *Effect of carbon mass*: In order to vary the solid to liquid ratio experiments were undertaken using various masses of carbon. The solid in liquid concentrations and the specific surfaces are shown in Table 5 and the k_s values are listed in

TABLE 5—DATA USED TO STUDY THE EFFECT OF VARYING CARBON MASS, W

Carbon mass W(g)	Carbon concentration m ($g dm^{-3}$)	Specific surface S_s (cm^{-1})
2.6	1.53	0.158
3.0	1.76	0.182
3.4	2.00	0.207
3.8	2.24	0.231
4.6	2.71	0.280

Table 2. The data are plotted in terms of the dimensionless mass transfer correlation $Sh/Sc^{0.33}$ against carbon mass on logarithmic co-ordinates and linear variation is observed (Fig. 7).

Conclusion: The surface processes which influence the initial uptake of Basic Yellow Dye on carbon have been studied. A model has been

Fig. 7. The adsorption of Basic Yellow 2G dye on activated carbon for various masses of carbon.

considered which enables the surface mass transfer coefficients to be determined and correlated in the form $Sh/Sc^{0.33}$. The dimensionless mass transfer function has been found to vary linearly with such variables as agitation, initial dye concentration, carbon particle size, dye solution, temperature and mass of carbon, when both parameters are plotted on logarithmic coordinates.

Explanation of symbols

- a constant in Langmuir isotherm, $cm^3 g^{-1}$
- C_t concentration of dye in bulk liquid, $mg l^{-1}$
- C_s concentration in liquid at outer surface of particle
- C_r concentration in liquid-filled pore at radius r
- C_0 concentration in bulk liquid at $t=0$
- C_m concentration in bulk liquid at equilibrium
- d_p particle diameter (cm)
- D_i impeller diameter
- D molecular diffusivity of dye in water, $cm^2 s^{-1}$
- D_t total effective diffusivity in particles, $cm^2 s^{-1}$
- k_s surface mass transfer coefficient, $cm s^{-1}$
- K adsorption equilibrium constant, $cm^3 g^{-1}$ carbon
- m mass of carbon particles per unit volume of particle free slurry, $g cm^{-3}$
- n_r concentration of adsorbed dye at radius r of particle, $mg dye g^{-1}$ carbon
- r radial co-ordinate in carbon particle, cm
- Sc Schmidt number, ν/D
- Sh Sherwood number, $k_s d_p/D$
- S_s outer surface of carbon particles per unit volume of particle free slurry, cm^{-1}
- t time, m, s
- ϵ_p porosity of carbon particle
- ν kinematic viscosity, $cm^2 s^{-1}$
- ρ_L density of particle free liquid, $g cm^{-3}$
- ρ_p density of carbon particle, $g cm^{-3}$

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